

possibly AI - by submitting comments and reviews of this post that include contributions to open science in 2023 that are important to themselves.

1. Anniversaries were celebrated

Recent accomplishments in open science policy and practice are the result of an incredible history of advocacy and advancement that set the stage for the year of open science. In 2023, a few of these events just-so-happened to fall on milestone anniversary dates. Here are five such anniversaries that were personally important to me throughout the past year:

April 30th, 1993

Thirty years ago - and five years before the practice would be known as open-source software sharing - [CERN released the source code](#) for the World Wide Web royalty-free. There is hardly anything more worth saying about the importance of this release - it's self-evident that the technological readiness of open science was made possible by CERN's precedent.

February 14th, 2002, April 11th, 2003, and October 22nd, 2003

Okay, so technically these are three dates but they're all related to an incredibly important aspect of the open science movement that they warranted being grouped together. These dates are the anniversaries of the signing of three declarations within a year of one another that galvanized open access as the most equitable model to sharing scholarly research publications. The [Budapest Open Access Initiative](#), the first among the three, was agnostic about business models and noted that there was room for innovation in the funding space for what we now call - [and what are now referenced in the updated Budapest recommendations](#) - green, gold, and diamond open access models. A year later, the [Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing](#) in April of 2003 defined that an open access publication had broad use and re-use rights, including for derivative works. While both Budapest and Bethesda were primarily focused on biomedical research communities, the [Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities](#) in October of 2003 was more inclusive across research disciplines and directly acknowledged the importance of the digital transformation from print to online formats in facilitating open access models. Of course, open access as a practice had been around for a bit longer but these twentyish-year anniversaries during the year of open science are worth commemorating as the coalescing forces that made zero-embargo possible in 2023 and beyond.

January 11th, 2013

The [year of open science was announced](#), perhaps coincidentally, on the ten-year anniversary of the death of [Aaron Swartz](#). Aaron was an activist, advocate, and champion of making information accessible to everyone. He helped found some of the most important open-source and open-access initiatives and resources at our disposal on the internet today. I encourage you to read the wikipedia page on Aaron and his

legacy in the open science movement. Personally, I've dedicated my year of open science to his memory and have donated [to Creative Commons](#), which he helped build. Not all anniversaries are happy ones - they can be, however, meaningfully inspiring to do right in the world.

February 22nd, 2013

It was lost on nobody in the community that the timing for the major federal science funding agency public access update plans to be submitted to OSTP would fall around the ten-year-anniversary of the Holdren Memo in February of 2023. After all, the 2022 Nelson Memo, along with the presentations and documents promoting it, referenced that a decade of sociotechnical progress had been made since the precedent setting Holdren Memo was released. What OSTP did ten years ago set the stage for the year of open science in 2023 - federally funded publications, data, metadata, and more should be shared freely with the public in an open, equitable, and secure manner! The 2022 Nelson Memo also fell on an important anniversary - it was the 80th anniversary of sociologist Robert K Merton arguing in 1942 that research publications should be made a public good: *"each researcher must contribute to the 'common pot' and give up intellectual property rights to allow knowledge to move forward."*

July 17th, 2018

Just five years ago, the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine published a consensus study report by the Committee on Toward and Open Science Enterprise titled, [Open Science by Design](#). The report was holistic in scope and read like a roadmap from vision, to strategy, to implementation of open science policies and practices that would result in a major shift for opening up how science is conducted and communicated. As of 2023, the vision articulated by the title and content of the report has not been fully realized; however, the scientific community-including funders, researchers, and policymakers-have clearly been following this roadmap. By the end of the 21st Century, I suspect, we'll be there and the coming year would be an excellent time to assess how far we've come.

2. Public access plans were updated

Throughout the year, several US federal agencies released their updated or new public access plans for public comment. A few excerpts from these plans that I personally think are worth highlighting include: The [National Institutes of Health's plan](#) to develop possible rights retention guidance to authors; The Director of the National Science Foundation including a cover letter in [their plan](#) that doubles down on the foundation's "unwavering commitment to open science"; the Department of Energy's incorporation of ORCID's and DOIs directly into the Department's [new public access plan](#); and NASA's expectation that open source code supported by their funded research will be shared as a public access asset under the Agency's [revised plan](#).

There are just too many gems throughout the federal funding community plans to share here - both open.science.gov and science.gov are great resources to stay up-to-date as agencies move into implementation phases of their plans in the coming year. There were lots of great things happening outside of the US too with respect to public access. For instance, Coalition-S announced that Plan-S in Europe would move toward more responsible models of [open access](#) publishing. That announcement came on the heels of the European Council's [call for immediate and equitable access](#) to publicly funded research. Public access to scientific research has truly expanded around the globe during 2023 and that momentum will continue throughout the coming years.

3. New resources for the community and by the community were released

One of the most exciting things to transpire over the last year was the proliferation of new open science resources throughout the community. I was thrilled about the [NASA TOPS Open Science Curriculum](#) being distributed online - it's free, comprehensive, self-guided and automatically integrates into certifications for credit upon completion via Credly to ORCID and LinkedIn. To close out my year, I actually [completed the course](#) and found that I learned a lot in the process. I saw lots of academic institutions update online guides to open science resources, such as this nice compendium by [Arizona State University](#).

Other resources that caught my attention included the many open science projects that federal agencies supported throughout the year. The Wilson Center compiled a useful round-up of [some of these projects](#) - many were already established and got a big boost during the year of open science. As a data geek, the open data projects promoted throughout the year were particularly interesting to me - especially those that move toward greater understanding of global issues like climate and cancer. For instance, the [Open Pediatric Brain Tumor Atlas](#), which builds upon the initial atlas supported by the [National Cancer Institute's Childhood Cancer Data Initiative](#) was published in 2023. I also saw that the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration released more than [24 petabytes of open climate data](#) to the public. Additionally, as someone who started their graduate education [studying disaster responses](#) using open data, I was ecstatic to see the Federation of American Scientists publish a call to action for a national [Open Disaster Data Initiative](#). Resources like these help accelerate discovery for the public good - whether that's for basic research or translation into practical solutions for complex problems.

4. Stakeholders embraced the movement

Enthusiasm for the year of open science spread broadly across the scientific community throughout 2023. It was encouraging to see so many stakeholders - including publishers, academic institutions, think-tanks, and scholarly societies reaffirm or newly embrace the values of open science. I could not possibly summarize all of the activities from so many

diverse stakeholders; thankfully, a few organizations have provided end-of-the-year round-ups:

- Many university libraries participated in the year of open science with an incredible array of activities throughout the year. The [Carnegie Mellon University Libraries](#) hosted a year-long series of events, including a lecture series, a hack-a-thon, and an open science symposium. Meanwhile, the [University of California San Francisco Library](#) described how the emphasis on equity in science has become a pillar of the open science movement in their end-of-year summary.
- Think-tanks, science consortia, and other not-for-profit brain trusts have a lot to benefit from participating in open science and the year of open science saw many of these institutions participate in diverse ways. The [International Science Council](#) summarized a laundry-list of discovery, advocacy, and position statements about open science from around the world in their end-of-year roundup. The [Wilson Center](#) gave some insights in how the open science movement invested new resources into the development of open source software and hardware. CERN teamed up with NASA and [hosted a summit](#) titled *Accelerating the Adoption of Open Science*, which I had the honor of attending-the summit [closing statement](#) affirmed participants' willingness to put open science into action at their home institutions.
- One of the best surprises, at least to me, was learning how many publishers and scholarly societies embraced the year of open science and made strides to explore how to reform academic publishing to reduce costs, improve access, and reach a broader audience. For instance, [Orvium described](#) how Oxford University Press was moving toward more sustainable models of publishing - intentions also expressed by the [American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology](#) - including innovation in how inequitable article processing charges are assessed. Frontiers, meanwhile, introduced their [open science charter at COP28](#) that demands such costs are communicated clearly and transparently, and correlate directly to the true costs of publishing (and I'm assuming that means without exorbitant excess revenue). There was some fun too, from publishers, including the double-feature issue of AGU-News rounding out the year of open science that included an editorial and word-search both titled [Wide. Open. Science.](#)

5. Discoveries were made

The open science movement is all for naught if discoveries are not made that result from greater transparency, inclusion, and access to research and data. While I've been primarily focused on open science policy and practice, I tried hard to stay abreast of the academic literature throughout the year as well. Here are three discoveries that I found to be of great interest related to open science this past year:

- First, Webb Telescope data, which is provided nearly immediately open to the world, led to the discovery of the most [distant supermassive blackhole known](#) to date.
- In many ways, the COVID-19 pandemic made the importance of the open science movement concrete and apparent to the public. We're still learning the lessons from COVID-19 and, thankfully, we'll continue to benefit from the open access to research and data that led to the rapid development of risk-mediating strategies, technologies, and treatments against SarsCov2. Now, there's a completely [open pipeline that has led to novel discoveries](#) to battle the virus well into the future.
- Finally, a reminder that data sometimes has cultural or societal sensitivities that must be considered when designing a data management and sharing plan. I was fascinated by this story of how the DNA from [27 enslaved persons buried near the Maryland Catocin Furnace](#) were analyzed in the context of the huge 23andMe database in a marvelous example of how forensic genomics can be used for good. I've been skeptical of the unencumbered use of large-scale genomics databases though for policing forensics and marketing uses.

A final thought to close out this year

This past year was simply *a year* and not *the year* of open science. Looking forward into 2024 and beyond, I am incredibly hopeful and optimistic for the future of science. With broader adoption of the principles, policies, practices and products of open science that have proliferated throughout 2023, it will be easier, more rewarding, and more equitable for all to learn, engage, produce, share, and collaborate in the scientific enterprise. That is to say, we are steadily moving toward a future where there is no distinction between science and open science - a future where science is truly open by design.

Happy New Year of Open Science!

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